

The Phonogrammarchiv of the Austrian Academy of Sciences

GERDA LECHLEITNER

The Phonogrammarchiv of the Austrian Academy of Sciences is the world's first research sound archive. To some extent it seems to be a paradox to introduce this "aged" institution in the first volume of a brand new journal. But then, its existence since 1899 proves the importance of that kind of institution until today, matched by experience and steady changes due to technical and knowledge-based developments. Focused on the three keywords "foundation – continuation – challenges" a brief insight into the Phonogrammarchiv will be given.

Foundation: ideas – strategies – implementation

On 27 April 1899, Sigmund Exner (Fig. 1), a famous physiologist of his time, together with colleagues from the humanities and sciences, brought forward the motion for founding "a kind of phonographic archive" (Exner 1900: 1). Those scientists were driven by the idea to use the rather new invention of sound recording by Th. A. Edison for research, and they were convinced that this new technology would offer new scientific approaches and research methods. There was no doubt that only sound recordings, allowing repeatable and controlled evaluation of sound phenomena, could provide the necessary basis for a wide range of disciplines, such as comparative musicology, comparative linguistics, dialectology or phonetics.

Moreover, the founders of the Phonogrammarchiv were aware of the importance of sound recordings not only as scientific sources, but also as documents representing cultural heritage. Therefore the Phonogrammarchiv has obtained an exceptional position: since its foundation it has been one of the institutes housed under the roof of the Austrian Academy of Sciences, which means that the Phonogrammarchiv has had to act as both a research institute and an archive – a fact also intended by the founding members.

In the founding motion three main collection areas were distinguished: firstly, languages comprising the typical standard German spoken around 1900, followed by various German dialects, extending into European languages and finally covering languages from all over the world; secondly, music, focused on non-European music as the basis for comparative musicology; and thirdly, voice portraits, recordings of renowned personalities from politics, the sciences and arts (cf. Exner 1900: 2-3). Those categories were soon enlarged by so-called *varia*, e.g. by animal sounds, castrato voices, children's voices or crying, but also shots. Traceability in respect of content and sound (timbre) was now possible; thus, the recordings should not only be produced, but also stored in an archive and consequently serve as documents, as sources for further research. These thoughts were triggered by the knowledge of traditions changing or even vanishing and by the awareness of new analyses and transcription methods. The Phonogrammarchiv's holdings comprise "scientific sound recordings" indicating that the acoustic sources result from controlled and documented situations; the recordings were made by scholars in the course of their research projects as sources for their envisaged work.

Finally, the starting point for the establishment of a sound archive in Vienna was somehow different from elsewhere. There was no need to organise already existing sound collections (as it was done in other archives), but the idea was rather to establish the theoretical background of archiving with its technical and content-related implications. Archiving in a pragmatic sense means to preserve the holdings in their best technical quality, combined with a comprehensive documentation including technical data, content information as well as the personal details of those recorded.

The regular recording activities started only in 1901 when the Archiv-Phonograph – newly invented especially for archival demands – was put to the test, both in the field and in the studio (Fig. 2-5). The recordings of 1901 reflect the various tasks addressed in the founding motion. In the archive (in the studio) recordings of several languages – such as German (standard language and dialects), Romanian, Walloon and Japanese – were made, as well as voice portraits of renowned contemporaries. The Archiv-Phonograph was also tested under different travel conditions (cf. Exner 1902), namely during the expeditions to Croatia, Brazil and the Isle of Lesbos. Until the outbreak of World War I, these activities were successfully continued and expeditions were conducted worldwide; during the war soldier songs of all languages spoken in the Austro-Hungarian Empire were recorded and recording sessions (for language and music studies) were done in prisoner-of-war camps. The interwar period was characterised by lack of money

and allowed recordings mainly on the continent; a further break was during World War II, and afterwards activities restarted slowly but steadily.

Continuation: 118 years of audio-visual archiving

The strategies just described were followed over the years – the collections increased thanks to the contribution by researchers who cooperated with the archive (i.e. they borrowed the recording machines and were instructed how to handle the technical equipment in order to achieve valuable recordings). Yet also the archive's staff added sound and, later on, video documents, mostly focused on cultural diversity in Vienna, but also on new approaches of music making in rural areas, dialectological studies or contact linguistics as well as special projects, e.g. in cultural anthropology (see below). Recently, collections compiled without the archive's support have been acquired, because their creators recognised the importance of those sound documents and would now like to make them accessible for further research. All in all, the recordings preserved in the Phonogrammarchiv might be called a mirror of Austrian research. As per February 2017, the audio and video holdings comprise a total of 13,821 hours of playing time representing 75,409 items (i.e. archive numbers).

The technological improvement allowed for a gradually prolonged recording time, due to the change from the analogue (first acoustic, then electrical) to the digital format. At first, the recording situation was such that performers were asked to speak or sing as loud and clear as possible as well as directly into the horn, thus taking an unpleasant and unnatural position; in those days, the method of elicitation or interrogation was in use for music and spoken items. Subsequently, however, depending on the respective research goal, the documentation of whole events in participant observation more and more prevailed. From the beginning, the collection strategy has upheld the idea of openness with regard to contents (accepting recordings from any geographic region and discipline) and has also mirrored Austrian research activities, i.e. the research of scholars in cooperation with the Phonogrammarchiv.

The anthropologist Rudolf Pöch is called a pioneer in (multi-media) field research because he used a photo and film camera as well as a sound device during his field work, already in Papua New Guinea 1904-06 (Fig. 10). This model was not followed by all researchers but by some. Over time the huge photo and film cameras were replaced by smaller and smaller devices. Eventually, researchers became more and more interested in video filming so that the Phonogrammarchiv included video in its archival programme as well. Videos are handled similarly to sound recordings in the course of archiving. Thus, the Phonogrammarchiv started in 2001 to establish a video department and now truly represents an audio-visual archive. Moreover, the digital era required not only

shifting the collections and documentation from analogue to digital but also archiving digital born sources and using the central server for the preservation of all data.

In order to make the recordings accessible, the first catalogue was published in 1922, which implied some challenges for the editors; finally, the layout was outstanding and was followed by four more printed catalogues until 1974. The long cataloguing experience was an asset in the subsequent process of creating a data base, which resulted in today's digital catalogue and its online version (<http://catalog.phonogrammarchiv.at/>).

The Phonogrammarchiv has long been considered a forerunner in respect of archival duties; therefore, it has always taken up the role of adviser, technical consultant and cooperation partner. On the one hand, the Phonogrammarchiv stood as a model for other research sound archives, on the other hand the staff's expertise and experience from experiments in the field (e.g. with new technologies) were integrated into the daily work and into an exchange with scholars. Thus, the workflow of archiving as well as various in-depth considerations about audio-visual sources are always in discussion and refined. Moreover, such activities are reflected in conferences and personal exchanges, thanks to the affiliation with international associations (e.g. IASA, AES, ICTM).

Challenges: position in a new media world

The Phonogrammarchiv saw two turns of centuries: the idea of establishing the first research sound archive was outstanding around 1900. From 1899 until the outbreak of World War I in 1914 (a time span emotionally still related to the 19th century), the archive evolved according to the ideas of the founders and thus represented an institution active worldwide. The 20th century is characterised by human disasters and setbacks as well as by rapidly changing technologies which then resulted in our connected, "global" world in which the Phonogrammarchiv sustained its position, mainly thanks to its specific technical expertise – introducing new technologies but at the same time improving re-recording and thus preservation of historical recordings by means of modern technologies. In that respect the Phonogrammarchiv's efforts in preserving and digitizing sound documents worldwide were honoured by the "UNESCO/Jikji Memory of the World Prize 2007" with the objective of contributing to the preservation accessibility of documentary heritage as the common heritage of humanity (the prize money, intended to contribute to safeguarding an audiovisual collection, preferably from a country with developing economy, was spent on the digitization of the José Maceda Collection, an important corpus of ethnomusicological recordings held by the University of the Philippines; http://www.phonogrammarchiv.at/wwwnew/newsarchiv_e.htm, December 15, 2008). Moreover, already in 1999, the historical collections (1899-1950)

of the Phonogrammarchiv were included as documents of universal significance in the World Register of UNESCO's "Memory of the World" Programme.

These glorious events heralded the 21st century which seems to be a demanding period. Besides those technical milestones and the handling of digital data as a matter of course, the archive faces the challenges caused by digital humanities and various platforms (being partner and provider of data, e.g. recognised as a CLARIN Knowledge Centre http://www.phonogrammarchiv.at/wwwnew/clarin-knowledge-centre_d.htm or listed in MERIL <http://portal.meril.eu/meril/view/facilitys/15816>). The Phonogrammarchiv is also in charge of intangible heritage, mostly concerning UNESCO's national list; in this respect archival holdings, as verifiable documents, and the expertise of staff members play an important role in the course of an application. The latest application dealt with RAVAG recordings, early and rare documents of Austrian folk music from 1934-1937; the folk music researcher, Georg Kotek, organised meetings with folk singers which were recorded by RAVAG, the former broadcasting cooperation. These shellac and decilith recordings are preserved in the Phonogrammarchiv and were digitised for the purpose of inscription (<https://www.unesco.at/kommunikation/dokumentenerbe/memory-of-austria/verzeichnis/detail/article/tonaufnahmen-der-ravag-volksliedersingen-aus-der-sammlung-kotek/>). Other inscriptions, e.g. dialects from Ötztal or Montafon, recordings of Roma musicians or Roma language, refer to sound documents in the archive among other documents. Moreover, archive staff are part of the consulting committee (s. <https://www.unesco.at/kultur/immaterielles-kulturerbe/umsetzung-in-oesterreich/fachbeirat/>).

Some of the latest projects should illustrate the Phonogrammarchiv's manifold activities and responsibilities. After the acquisition and detailed archival exploration of Mozes Heinschink's huge collection on Roma culture from the 1960s onwards, a main focus on Roma developed over the years. Two outstanding cooperation projects, "RomBase – didactically edited information on Roma", already finished in 2014 (<http://rombase.uni-graz.at/>), and the still ongoing "RomArchive – an international digital archive for art of the Roma", have to be mentioned. RomArchive focuses on their self-representation, generating new narratives and reflecting the heterogeneity of the Roma's diverse national and cultural identities. In addition to written literary texts, a representative selection of orally transmitted texts in different varieties of the Romani language, including metadata and advanced descriptions, has been contributed by the Phonogrammarchiv (<https://blog.romarchive.eu/?p=7396>).

Based on current (political) events the Phonogrammarchiv launched an interview project on the personal backgrounds and prospects of Syrian war refugees in Austria. Another recent project deals with "Death & Life: Local conceptions of reincarnation among the Druzes in the Middle East", with ethnological fieldwork carried out in different national contexts and in different social strata. Given the strong connection between *taqammuş* and violent events of death, research into *taqammuş* is highly topical in times

of war and trauma. Therefore, the present research project seeks to specifically interview Syrian Druze refugees.

The Phonogrammarchiv takes part in the project “Preservation and Transmission of Africa’s Collective Memory – African Testimonies and Oral Literature in Early Colonial History”, conducted by the foundation AfricAvenir International, which aims at giving the voice to African witnesses and actors during the early colonial period. With the Phonogrammarchiv’s help audio cassettes from the 1980s with interviews of old Cameroonian witnesses have been digitised, and master DVDs for publication will be prepared.

Together with the Austrian Institute for Chemistry and Technology (OFI) the Phonogrammarchiv has developed a method for the chemical restoration of acetate media. The method has been patented and will be further developed as part of a public-private-partnership. In this context, the Phonogrammarchiv will participate as partner within the European Union Horizon 2020 project *NEMOSINE: Innovative packaging solutions for storage and conservation of 20th century cultural heritage of artefacts based on cellulose derivate*, starting in 2018.

The Phonogrammarchiv is not only asked to be a partner in various projects (either more content related or more in technically oriented), but also in exhibitions. Archeo-Phonica was the title of an exhibition in Bolzano in 2017, where the early developments and activities of the record industry were contrasted with the Phonogrammarchiv’s role as research sound archive, together with the presentation of its earliest sound documents of Alto Adige.

Not to forget the Phonogrammarchiv’s publications, which also have significant effects in terms of outreach. Since 1999 the Complete Historical Collections 1899-1950 have been published as a CD edition, 16 series have so far been released (http://www.phonogrammarchiv.at/wwwnew/edition_e.htm). These series not only represent a commented source edition addressed to an interested public, especially in the regions of the recordings’ origin, and to the scientific community enabling easy access to the historical recordings, their original documentation and commentaries and discussions on the material from a modern perspective; they are also meant to “repatriate” cultural expressions of those recorded to their descendants. Meanwhile copies of some “younger” and comprehensive collections have also been handed over to those who originally collaborated with the researchers (e.g. Madagascar’s acoustic heritage in 2012, recordings of indigenous vocal music in Western Amazonia in 2017, see Fig. 11). Established in 2010 and since 2014 published by the Austrian Academy of Sciences Press under the title of “International Forum on Audio-Visual Research” (which reflects its focus), the Phonogrammarchiv’s Yearbook showcases the potential of the Phonogrammarchiv as an institution, as a repository and as a place of research, encounter and discussion, contributing new results (<http://www.austriaca.at/buecher?frames=yes>).

With the years and the growing number of necessary tasks, the number of staff members has increased and a (re)organisation has been undertaken. In the 1970s and ’80s the

director worked together with just one technician, two archivists (for ethnomusicology and linguistics) and the secretary. Nowadays, with 14 employees of various disciplines, a technical (including audio and video, IT management and systems administration), an archival (documentation, preservation and access management including legal issues) and a publication department have been established. An additional department has also been created: the RMB collection, founded by Rudolf M. Brandl, a former staff member, then professor of ethnomusicology at the University of Göttingen, and finally director of the Phonogrammarchiv (2007-2010). He deposited his collections (with a focus on Chinese opera and field research in Greece) in the archive with the goal to preserve, digitise and edit these sound documents. Although the employees' responsibilities are focused, networking among them takes place daily so that archival knowledge in general is necessary.

The archive is not a closed institution; preservation and documentation serve the purpose of giving access to the holdings and dealing with any inquiries coming in. The recordings are of interest mostly to researchers but also to the interested public, either for personal reasons (e.g. recorded relatives) or official events (e.g. exhibitions). The whole stock is searchable via the online catalogue (<http://catalog.phonogrammarchiv.at/>), including the main data of the collections, supplemented by short sound and video samples according to legal (moral and ethical) rights. Requests for distinct sound and video recordings in full length are subject to an agreement concerning the use of these items, and are delivered either as files (via data transfer) or on a CD-R; a small fee will be charged for such copies.

All these manifold activities prove that the Phonogrammarchiv is an active archive (the acquisition never has stopped) and “constructing” knowledge (by documentation and indexing). In this regard, the performer-researcher-archivist relationship has to be underlined. The different positions, responsibilities, respect and recognition owed to each other have to be reflected and kept in mind, resulting in discussions about the ethics of archives, about legal and moral rights and copyrights vis-à-vis those who deliver their knowledge and skills – especially in our global, cross-linked and open world. An archive does not show how the world, how life really has been, but it includes the exploration of what people thought it might have been. Discussions about the “position” of archives, the colonial traits and postcolonial discourses, and profound debates on and interpretation of the contexts are important. The Phonogrammarchiv's staff takes part in such discussions, and it is one of the archive's goals to keep a balance between technical and archival demands as well as content-related discussions.

FIGURE 1. Sigmund Exner (1846-1926), founder and first director (© Phonogrammarchiv).

FIGURE 2. Archiv-Phonograph Type I, 1900 (© Phonogrammarchiv).

FIGURE 3. Archiv-Phonograph Type III, 1906-1910 (© Phonogrammarchiv).

FIGURE 4. Archiv-Phonograph Type V, 1927–1931 (© Phonogrammarchiv).

FIGURE 5. “Phonograms”: Wax disc, metal disc, epoxy resin cast (© Phonogrammarchiv).

FIGURE 6. František Pospíšil: field work in South Moravia, Dobro Polje (Guttenfeld), 1910 (©Phonogrammarchiv).

- Triller; Embutu (einfellige Konustrommel), Nankasa (einfellige Konustrommel), Empunyi (einfellige Konustrommel), Enasai (Kürbissassel), Eisenglocke, wenn nicht anders angegeben.
- B 4864 Tanzlied.
- B 4865 Lied auf Muwanga (Erfinder der Trommelmusik). Zusätzlich Pfofe.
- B 4866 Preislied auf den Häuptling Ndawula.
- B 4867 Preislied auf den Häuptling Ndawula. Zusätzlich Pfofe.
- B 4868 Preislied auf Bulange, das Haus von Kabaka, dem König von Buganda. Zusätzlich Händeklatschen.
- B 4869—4870 Lieder der Baganda. Gesungen von einem Muganda-Knaben, ca. 15, Schüler, geb. bei Nkokonjeru. Aufgenommen in Nkokonjeru, Uganda. Männersolo.
- B 4869 „Tugenze, tugenze...“
- B 4870 „Enyonyi bwe ziyimba...“
- B 4871 Missionslied der Baganda. Gesungen vom Missionskinderchor aus Nkokonjeru, 7—16, Schüler. Aufgenommen in Nkokonjeru, Uganda. „Ogenda wa?“ Einstimmiger Kinderchor.
- B 4872 Luganda-Sprache. Gesprochen von einem Mädchen, ca. 7, Schülerin. Aufgenommen in Nkokonjeru, Uganda. Gedicht.
- B 4873 Lied der Baganda. Gesungen von drei Mädchen, 7—10, Schülerinnen. Aufgenommen in Nkokonjeru, Uganda. Spiellied: „Kwese nawutira akagoma“. Einstimmiger Kindergesang.
- B 4874 Englisch, gesprochen von einem Muganda-Knaben, 11, Schüler. Aufgenommen in Nkokonjeru, Uganda. Englisches Gedicht: „My name is Stephen Younger...“
- B 4875 Luganda-Sprache. Gesprochen von einer Muganda-Frau, geb. bei Nkokonjeru. Aufgenommen in Nkokonjeru, Uganda. Über das Kochen.
- B 4876—4885 Lieder und Instrumentalmusik der Baganda. Gespielt und gesungen von Evaristo Muyinda, Musiklehrer. Aufgenommen in Kampala, Uganda.
- B 4876 Lied: „Ganga alula“. Männersolo und Ennanga (Bogenharfe).
- B 4877 Enderre-Solo (Bambuskerbflöte): „Ana mwanganga“.
- B 4878 Lied: „Omukanya bulo atuyanye“. Männersolo und Entongoli (Leier).
- B 4879 Endingidi-Solo (einsaitige Röhrengeige): „Abomu Kampala muje tuserere“.
- B 4880 Lied: „Abayinda mukulike entalo“. Männersolo und Leier.
- B 4881 Lied: „Omweabutwa wakyeye“. Männersolo und Bogenharfe.
- B 4882 Gespräch in Englisch über Harfe und Leier zwischen Livingstone Katongole, einem Muganda, Schüler von Evaristo Muyinda, und Gerhard Kubik.
- B 4883 Enderre-Solo (Bambuskerbflöte): „Omusango gwa balere“.
- B 4884 Lied: „Ensimi bwe zikugwako ngobala engero“. Männersolo und Endingidi (einsaitige Röhrengeige).
- B 4885 Stimmung der Amadinda (Liegezylophon): a) Aufnahme im Museum, b) Aufnahme im Freien, c) Spiel in Oktavenparallelen.
- B 4886—4887 Amadinda-Solo (Liegezylophon). Gespielt von Evaristo Muyinda, einem Muganda, Musiklehrer, und J. O. Obalokor, einem Acholi, Musiker, und Gerhard Kubik.
- B 4886 „Sematimba ne Kikwabanga“.
- B 4887 „Obutala Ob'e Nkasa“. Gespielt mit a) dünnen Stäbchen, b) dicken Stäbchen.
- B 4888—4924 Musik aus der Blindenschule in Salama, Uganda. Aufgenommen in Salama, Uganda.
- B 4888—4906 Instrumentalmusik blinder Musiker. Gespielt von Blinden verschiedener Stämme Ugandas. Akadinda (Xylophon), Embutu und Empunyi (zweifellige Konustrommeln), Engalabi (Bechertrommel), Nankasa (Trommel), Enasai und Ensege (Rasseln), wenn nicht anders angegeben.
- B 4888 „Omusalaba“.
- B 4889 Titel unbekannt.
- B 4890 „Songola katt“.
- B 4891 „Singa namera byoya singa mbuse“.
- B 4892 „Songola katt“.
- B 4893 „Njagala okudayo e Bukunja“.
- B 4894 „Omusalaba“.
- B 4895 „Kisowa kya mwabutwa kivedemu emwanyo“. Zusätzlich einstimmiger Männergesang.
- B 4896 „Kisowa kya mwabutwa kivedemu emwanyo“. (Unvollständiges Ensemble).
- B 4897 „Singa namera byoya singa mbuse“. Zusätzlich einstimmiger Männergesang; Endingidi (einsaitige Röhrengeige), Enderre (Bambuskerbflöte).
- B 4898 „Njagala okudayo e Bukunja“. Zusätzlich einstimmiger Männergesang; Endingidi (einsaitige Röhrengeige) und Enderre (Bambuskerbflöte).
- B 4899 Stimmung der Akadinda.
- B 4900 „Njagala okudayo e Bukunja“.
- B 4901 „Omugenyi agenda kyadanda“.
- B 4902 „Balinserekerera balinsala ekyambe“.
- B 4903 „Bogerera mvogerere“.
- B 4904 „Bogerera mvogerere“.
- B 4905 Titel unbekannt.
- B 4906 „Bogerera mvogerere“.
- B 4907—4911 Lieder eines fahrenden Sängers. Gesungen und gespielt von Mukama, einem Mugwera, Musiker, geb. Kachuru, Bugwera, Uganda, gespielt von Joufeu Bosa, einem Muganda, Musiklehrer, und einem Musoga.
- B 4907 „Galivunda“. Männersolo; zwei Kadongo (Sansen).
- B 4908 „Owalyanu webale“. Männersolo; drei Kadongo (Sansen).
- B 4909 „Galivunda“ (andere Version). Männersolo; drei Kadongo (Sansen).
- B 4910 „Kwini“. Männersolo und einstimmiger Männergesang; zwei Kadongo (Sansen).

FIGURE 7. Photo of the 1966 catalogue of the recording (Hermann, Schendl and Schüller 1966).

<p style="text-align: center;">4886 488</p> <p style="text-align: center;">4887</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Band Nr. _____ Aufnahme Nr. <u>84-75</u></p> <h3 style="text-align: center;">Des Phonographierten</h3> <p>1. Vor- und Zuname <u>Evaristo Miyinda</u></p> <p>Geschlecht <u>m</u> Volk, (Stamm, Muttersprache) <u>Miganda</u> Alter <u>43</u> Beruf <u>Musiklehrer und Orchesterleiter</u></p> <p>Geburtsort, Land <u>Ort unbekannt, eingeborene Landbezeichnung: Buganda, Staat: Uganda.</u> Aufgewachsen in <u>Buganda</u></p> <p>Längere Aufenthalte in <u>Kampala, am Hof des Kabaka (König von Buganda) und im Uganda Museum.</u></p> <p>Jetziger Wohnort <u>c/o Uganda Museum Kampala.</u></p> <p>Heimat des Vaters _____ der Mutter <u>Buganda</u></p> <h3 style="text-align: center;">Des Phonographierten</h3> <p>2. Vor- und Zuname <u>J. O Obaloker</u></p> <p>Geschlecht <u>m</u> Volk, (Stamm, Muttersprache) <u>Acholi</u> Alter <u>ca. 30</u> Beruf <u>Musiker</u></p> <p>Geburtsort, Land <u>Ort unbekannt, eingeborene Landbezeichnung Acholi, Uganda.</u> Aufgewachsen in <u>Acholi-Land, Uganda.</u></p> <p>Längere Aufenthalte in <u>Kampala,</u></p> <p>Jetziger Wohnort <u>c/o Uganda Museum, Kampala.</u></p> <p>Heimat des Vaters _____ der Mutter <u>Acholi-Land</u></p> <p>3. Gerhard Kubik, m, Oesterreicher, 25 Jahre alt, Musikethnologe, geboren in Wien, Oesterreich, Schüler im afrikanischen Xylophonspiel bei Mr. Evaristo Miyinda.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Bandgeschwindigkeit <u>9 1/2 rpm</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Umdrehungszahl <u>Vollrpm</u></p> <h3 style="text-align: center;">Der Aufnahme</h3> <p>Datum, Ort, Land <u>Februar 1960, Kampala, Uganda</u></p> <p>Sprache, Mundart <u>Luganda</u></p> <p>Gegenstand <u>Musik für das Kiganda-Xylophon Amadinda.</u></p> <p>Musik, vokal oder instrumental _____ <u>XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX</u></p> <p>Stimmgattung oder Instrumente _____</p> <p>Technische Daten <u>Orig. Holzer-Magnette, 9cm Halb-spinn, Tonbandkopf + 100 Bel. - Herris: Z. Maxrad, Selbstspann M23, 9 1/2 rpm, 2Kapseln, Tonbandstoff HF 12</u></p> <p>Aufgenommen durch <u>den Miganda-Musiker "Livingstone"</u></p> <p>wissenschaftl. Kontrolle <u>Gerhard Kubik</u></p> <p>4886 <u>grüner Tonpapier, ca 582</u> 1'08" <u>Amadinda - Trink</u> <u>"Sematimba ne Kikwabanga" (Sematimba und Kikwabanga)</u> <u>(Neu von Angalam nian Beilage)</u> <u>(Im Freien aufgenommen)</u></p> <p>4887 <u>blauer Tonpapier, ca 599</u> 1'52" <u>Amadinda - Trink</u> <u>"Oulatao Dine Nsinsi" (Der Kampf von Nsinsi)</u> <u>2) mit dünnen Häbeln</u> <u>6) "dieken"</u> <u>(die dünnen Häbeln sind die normalen die dünnen die Häbeln für die Hörler)</u></p>
--	---

FIGURE 8

z. Nr. 4886
m. Nr. 4887

Kiganda-Amadinda aus
Nkokonjeru, Uganda.

Der Lusambya-Baum,
aus dem die Amadinda-
Tasten verfertigt werden.

FIGURES 8-9. Scans of the original handwritten and typed protocols, corresponding to the archival numbers 4886 and 4887 + the attached photographs. (© Phonogrammarchiv).

FIGURE 10. Rudolf Pöch: field work in Papua New Guinea, Cape Nelson, 1905 (© Phonogrammarchiv).

FIGURE 11. Repatriation of recordings of indigenous vocal music from Western Amazonia, July 16, 2017 (photo provided by Juan Rubén Ruiz Zevallos, indigenous university UCSS Nopoki Atalaya, UCSS-NOPOKI).

References (a selection)

Brandl, Rudolf and Dietrich Schüller

- 1969/70 “Das Phonogrammarchiv der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften”, *Wiener Völkerkundliche Mitteilungen*, XVI-XVII/11-12: 117-130.

Exner, Sigmund

- 1900 “Bericht über die Arbeiten der von der kaiserl. Akademie der Wissenschaften eingesetzten Commission zur Gründung eines Phonogramm-Archives”, *Anzeiger der mathematisch-naturwissenschaftlichen Klasse*, 37 (Beilage): 1-6 (1. Mitteilung der Phonogrammarchivs-Kommission).
- 1902 “II. Bericht über den Stand der Arbeiten der Phonogramm-Archivs-Commission”, *Anzeiger der mathematisch-naturwissenschaftlichen Klasse*, 39 (Beilage): 1-31 (2. Mitteilung der Phonogrammarchivs-Kommission).

Fennesz-Juhasz, Christiane and Nadja Wallaszkovits

- 2015 “Transferring Archival Research Collections into the Digital Domain: A Special Challenge”, in Gerda Lechleitner and Christian Liebl (eds.), *International Forum on Audio-Visual Research/ Jahrbuch des Phonogrammarchivs*, VI: 126-143.

Graf, Walter

- 1964 “Aus der Geschichte des Phonogrammarchivs der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften”, *Bulletin phonographique*, VI: 9-39.

Hajek, Leo

- 1928 “Das Phonogrammarchiv der Akademie der Wissenschaften in Wien von seiner Gründung bis zur Neueinrichtung im Jahre 1927”, *Sitzungsberichte der phil.-hist. Klasse 207/3*: 1-22. (58. Mitteilungen der Phonogrammarchivs-Kommission).

Hermann, Elfriede, Herbert Schendl, and Dietrich Schüller

- 1966 (eds.), *Katalog der Tonbandaufnahmen B 3001 - 7000 des Phonogrammarchives der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften in Wien*. Graz-Wien-Köln, Hermann Böhlaus Nachf. (82. Mitteilung der Phonogrammarchivs-Kommission).

Kowar, Helmut

- 2017 “‘Die Anlage einer Art phonographischen Archives’ – mehr als ein Archiv. Ein Überblick über die Geschichte des Phonogrammarchivs der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften”, *Geistes-, sozial- und kulturwissenschaftlicher Anzeiger*, CLII/1: 5-45 (94. Mitteilungen des Phonogrammarchivs).

Pavuz, Franz

- 2012 “10 Jahre Videographie am Phonogrammarchiv”, in Gerda Lechleitner and Christian Liebl (eds.), *Jahrbuch des Phonogrammarchivs der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften*, III: 26-34.
- 2016 “First Migration: Results and Experiences”, in Gerda Lechleitner and Christian Liebl (eds.), *International Forum on Audio-Visual Research/ Jahrbuch des Phonogrammarchivs*, VII: 167-173.

Pösch, Rudolf

- 1917 “Technik und Wert des Sammelns phonographischer Sprachproben auf Expeditionen”, *Sitzungsberichte der mathematisch-naturwissenschaftlichen Klasse*, III/126: 1-13 (45. Mitteilungen der Phonogrammarchivs-Kommission).

Schüller, Dietrich and Albrecht Häfner

- 2014 *Handling and Storage of Audio and Video Carriers* [<http://www.iasa-web.org/handling-storage-tc05>] (IASA Technical Committee – Standards, Recommended Practices and Strategies, IASA-TC 05).

Seeger, Anthony and Shuba Chaudhuri

- 2004 (eds.), *Archives for the Future. Global Perspectives on Audiovisual Archives in the 21st century*, Calcutta, Seagull Books.

Wallaskovits, Nadja

- 2013 “Digitization of Small Collections: Problems and Solutions”, in L. Duranti and E. Shaffer (eds.), *The Memory of the World in the Digital Age: Digitization and Preservation. An international conference on permanent access to digital documentary heritage*, UNESCO, Vancouver (Canada): 1440-1450. (http://ciscra.org/docs/UNESCO_MOW2012_Proceedings_FINAL_ENG_Compressed.pdf).

